

ANALYSIS OF ESCIN-CONTAINING RAW MATERIALS

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Introduction. Following the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 21, 2022, PD-55 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of the pharmaceutical industry of the Republic in 2022-2026", it has been established that industry experts should improve the provision of high-quality, effective, and safe pharmaceutical products to the population. This includes increasing production volume by three times through the introduction of advanced scientific and technical achievements and innovations to the pharmaceutical industry, and raising the level of provision of the domestic market to 80%. Additionally, the Concept of development of the pharmaceutical industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2024 plans to organize and localize the production of substances using medicinal plants as a source of medicines. Finding local raw materials with sufficient reserves to obtain such medicinal substances is crucial. Our country is rich in medicinal plants, including horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum* L.), which is grown as an ornamental tree. Its seeds contain triterpene glycosides, flavonoids, coumarins, and other bioactive compounds. 30 kinds of triterpene glycosides were identified in horse chestnut seeds, with its main active compound being escin. This research presents the results of the study of triterpene glycosides contained in horse chestnut seeds grown in different regions of our country and abroad.

Aim. The work aims to analyze triterpene glycosides in horse chestnut seeds grown in different countries.

Methods. Horse chestnut seeds grown in the cities of Tashkent, Gazalkent and Istanbul were used in the research. The samples were analyzed by Liquid Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometry (Shimadzu, LC-MS 2020).

Results: Triterpene glycosides and their derivatives were extracted from raw materials gathered from three different regions using established methods. The components isolated were analyzed using the LC-MS method in ESI-MS negative ion mode, and the analysis was performed by comparing them with

standard samples of escin (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Horse chestnut seeds from Tashkent city, Uzbekistan were found to contain $5.2 \pm 1.3\%$ triterpene glycosides. Additionally, triterpene glycosides were also observed in horse chestnut seeds from Gazalkent, Tashkent region, and Istanbul, Turkey. The percentage of triterpene glycosides in the horse chestnut seeds from Istanbul was $3.94 \pm 1.4\%$, while the proportion in samples from Gazalkent city was $5.04 \pm 1.1\%$. All samples were analyzed using ESI-MS, and compounds with mass-to-charge ratios of $[M-H]^-$ 1129, 1099, 1131, 1113, 1089, 1117, and 1057 were identified. These mass-to-charge ratios correspond to escin and its isomers and derivatives. It was observed that escin and its derivatives in horse chestnut seeds from the regions of Uzbekistan and Turkey are qualitatively similar, but they vary slightly in quantity. The order of decreasing proportion of triterpene glycosides in horse chestnuts from different regions was established as follows: Tashkent city (5.2%) > Gazalkent (5.04%) > Istanbul (3.94%).

Conclusion: A comparative study was conducted for the first time on triterpene glycosides in horse chestnut seeds from Uzbekistan and Turkey. The study confirmed that there is no difference in quality among the escin isomers and derivatives found in the seeds. Scientific research has shown that the seeds of local horse chestnut can serve as a significant source of escin production, which is crucial for the pharmaceutical industry.

